

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN TRANSLATING UZBEK FAIRY TALES

Ruziyeva Iroda Zokirovna

irodazokirovna96@gmail.com

Master student of Termez pedagogical
institute of TERSU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6572674>

Abstract

This article is devoted to the intercultural competence in Uzbek tales and translating problems of words and units which is related to this concept. It is shown differences between English and Uzbek culture in different tales .

Key words: intercultural, competence, humanity, sincere, quality, wisdom, conscientious, veracious ,enmity, courtesy ,cultural

DISCUSSION

Several aspects of intercultural competence warrant further comment. First, intercultural competence does not involve abandoning one's own cultural identifications or affiliations, nor does it require individuals to adopt the cultural practices, beliefs, discourses or values of other cultures.

Intercultural competence instead involves being open to, curious about and interested in people who have other cultural affiliations, and the ability to understand and interpret their practices, beliefs, discourses and values.

Intercultural competence enables people to interact and cooperate effectively and

appropriately in situations where cultural 'otherness' and 'difference' are salient. It also enables people to act as 'mediators' among people of different cultures, and to interpret and explain different perspectives. That said, encounters with people from other cultural orientations can be a source of personal development and enrichment if their perspectives are integrated into one's own sense of self.

Second, because intercultural competence involves learning about and interpreting other people's cultural perspectives and relating them to one's own, intercultural competent individuals are able to use their intercultural encounters to learn about and reflect critically on their own cultural affiliations. Due to the enculturation process in which cultural beliefs, values and practices are acquired particularly during childhood and adolescence, it can be difficult to psychologically decanter from one's own affiliations.

Intercultural competent individuals acquire a more critical awareness and understanding of their own cultural positioning, beliefs, discourses and values

through comparing and relating them to those of other people. For this reason, intercultural competence not only enhances one's knowledge and understanding of other people; it also enhances self-knowledge and self understanding.

Third, it is important to emphasize that language has a privileged role within intercultural encounters because it is the most important (although not the only) symbolic system which enables group members to share their cultural perspectives, beliefs and values.

There are a lot of differences between two nations their qualities, culture horizons. We can face them while translating some words and phrases.

The first signal of courtesy is a greeting. This side it is cultural difference between two nations.

As for that in Uzbek: "Assalomu alaykum" is used in any part of the day. But in English "Good morning" for morning time, "Good afternoon" for mid-day, "Good evening" for evening time. Translators will be careful in this phase. They try to take into consideration the sequence of events.

In some tales we can see good and bad sides of people. Their characters are revealed skillfully as for the nationality. E.g. Zumrad va Qimmat – Zumrad and

Kimmat. Zumrad is a kind honest, conscientious, veracious girl. We have to use the word "veracious" in the meaning of to'griso'z and haqiqatgo'y.

In interpreting "Iliqlik bilan salomlashdi" will be as greeted warmly. Usually we use warm for "nature", in this place it is used in identifying human nature. For "Qo'pollik bilan salomlashdi" we translated as greeted rudely. From that point one can realize the greeting process reveals what kind of people he or she.

About the fairy tale Uchog'a-ini botirlar - Three brave brothers, even it is difficult to find a suitable word for translating the name of the tale. As we know, "og'a- ini" this word is not existed in English language, as this means relatives but we use the word brothers instead.

Below we have analyzed some other samples in this tale:

Qo'rqoqbo'l maybotirbo'ldingiz – you are brave but not cowardly

Tog'ribo'ling – bexavotirbo'lasiz- be right you will be safe

Maqtanchoq bo'lmang – xijolat tortmaysiz – don't brag you won't be ashamed

Dangasa bo'lmang – baxtsiz bo'lmaysiz- don't be lazy, you won't be unhappy

Podshohlik- qonxo'rlikdir -the kingdom is a bloodbath

Birqoshiqqonimdano'ting – skip a spoon of my blood

Adovat- enmity

Most of these words of wisdom but their meaning are great. The old man used them as his motto to bring up his children as a real human. In every Uzbek tales it is used not only newly – coined words but also old Uzbek language. The word “podshoh” is used in ancient times, and in tales it shows respect to the people for their king. e.g. Podshohim, olampanoh –myking.

There are tales that every parent knows and must pass on to their child. Tales of warning and terror of those who break their vows and kill for no reason other than malice. Tales of saving the lovely princess from a prince that is much less than charming. And what it takes to bring her home rescuing babies from parents not to fit to raise them, and the reason no super natural can truly with such vile creatures. These are human tales¹. Fairy tales led to goodness. Every child brings up through different fairy tales. They help them to know himself or herself and broaden their horizons.

M. Gorky indicates that the basis of ancient fantasy was the desire to facilitate their work. Even the most daring ups of imagination are never abstract, always specific and meet the vital needs of a person, reflecting the reality. “Under each rise of ancient fantasy it is easy to discover its causative agent and this pathogen, says M. Gorky is always the desire of people to facilitate their work”².

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Tales heroes reflected humanity. It may be an animal or person. They are the face of human, humanity and their qualities. Our senses, characters and other features. While translating these words and phrases from Uzbek into English there are grammar and lexical problems. Because every nation has different notions.

Reference

1. O'zbek xalqertaklari 1-qism . “O'qituvchi” Nashriyot - matbaaijodiyuyi. Toshkent -2014 .(112-126p.)
2. Jack Zipes. Finding humanity through fairy tales . 2020
3. Vidhur Sharma . Fascinating tales of humanity . 2011.(202,p.)
4. Gorky.M.” About Fairy tales” <https://www.litres.ru/maksim-gorkiy/> (3p.)
5. <https://ziyouz.uz>.
6. <https://gulxan.uz>
7. <https://saviya.uz>

¹Jack Zipes. Finding Humanity through fairy tales

²Gorky.M.” About Fairy tales” <https://www.litres.ru/maksim-gorkiy/> (3p.)

